

Augelite Raman and ATR-IR Fingerprints obtained with q-Gaussian and q-BWF deconvolutions made by means of Fityk Software

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Abstract: This work is proposing the fingerprints of Raman and ATR-IR spectra of Augelite minerals. The Raman fingerprints are based on q-Gaussian functions deconvolution, whereas the ATR-IR fingerprints are obtained with q-Gaussian and q-BWF functions deconvolutions. q-Gaussian and q-BWF functions are implemented in Fityk software.

The first use of the term “fingerprint” in relation to the Raman spectroscopy seems to be in an article published in 1947 about the Raman spectra of hydrocarbons by Fenske and coworkers. Fenske et al., 1947, wrote that the “Raman lines, are characteristic of the substance illuminated and are therefore a “fingerprint” of that substance”. From that time on, the points of identification, such as positions of peaks, shoulders and valleys create the characteristic spectral pattern which is known as the “Raman fingerprint” of a given material. This pattern allows the material classification, “without any preliminary information about composition and structural origin of the individual features” (D’Ippolito et al., 2015).

Besides Raman spectra, we can consider the ‘fingerprints’ also of ATR-IR spectra. Here we determine both Raman and ATR-IR fingerprints for *Augelite minerals*. Data are kindly provided by the *RRUFF database* (Lafuente et al., 2015). We discussed the Raman and Attenuated Total Reflectance Infrared RRUFF spectra in Sparavigna, 2024.

The deconvolution of the Raman spectra (depolarized) is proposed determined by means of q-Gaussian functions. Deconvolutions are obtained using Fityk software (Wojdyr, 2010). The centers of the peaks and the parameters of the components are given in files .peaks by Fityk. The q-Gaussians are defined by Sparavigna in a script for this software. The deconvolution of the ATR-IR spectra is obtained with both q-BWF and q-Gaussian functions; in this case too, the functions are defined by Sparavigna with a script in Fityk. The q-Breit-Wigner-Fano function is an asymmetric form of the q-Gaussian function.

The mineral and its vibrational spectroscopy

Augelite is an aluminium phosphate mineral (formula: $\text{Al}_2(\text{PO}_4)(\text{OH})_3$). The crystal system is monoclinic (Dana et al., 1997). The augelite “occurs as a product of metamorphism of phosphate bearing peraluminous sediments and in high-temperature hydrothermal ore deposits. It occurs in association with attakolite, svanbergite, lazulite, hematite, trolleite, berlinite, rutile, pyrophyllite, baryte, arsenopyrite, stannite, pyrite, andorite, cassiterite and zinkenite” (Wikipedia, mentioning <https://rruff.geo.arizona.edu/doclib/hom/augelite.pdf>)

The investigation of the vibrational spectroscopy of natural augelite has been proposed by Frost and Weier (2004). In their abstract, the authors tell: “The vibrational spectra of natural augelite (Al₂(OH)₃(PO₄) including the infrared at 298 K and Raman spectra at 298 and 77 K have been obtained and related to the crystallography of the mineral. Bands are identified in terms of the fundamental vibrating units namely PO₄, Al₂OH and Al₃OH. The use of infrared and Raman OH stretching wavenumbers using a Libowitzky type function enabled hydrogen bond distances of 2.96, 2.84 and 2.72 Å to be estimated. The hydrogen bonds formed by the Al₂OH units are weaker than that of the Al₃OH units” (Frost & Weier, 2004).

For the spectral analyses, Frost and Weier used “Spectralcalc software package GRAMS. Band component analysis was undertaken using the Jandel ‘Peakfit’ software package, Band fitting was done using a Gauss–Lorentz cross-product function with the minimum number of component bands used for the fitting process. The Gauss Lorentz ratio was maintained at values greater than 0.7” (Frost & Weier, 2004). The GaussLorentz cross product functions are not given in the article by Frost and Weier. As we have already told in our discussion of Raman broad scans of Vivianite Group minerals, in Origin Help we find an expression which is governed by parameter “s” as shape. Probably, the “ratio” in Frost and Weier is the “shape” in Origin.

Hydroxyl stretching region

“The infrared and Raman spectra of the hydroxyl stretching region of augelite are shown in Fig. 3 [by Frost and Weier, 2004]. There are two crystallographic independent hydrogen bonds in augelite [Frost and Weier mentioning Araki et al., 1968] and two of the expected three ν(OH) bands are generated by correlation splitting in the symmetry correlated pairs of the OH groups in general positions” (Frost & Weier, 2004). “In the infrared spectrum strong bands are observed at **3538**, **3453** and **3326** cm⁻¹” (Frost & Weier, 2004). “The two higher wavenumber bands are assigned to the OH stretching vibrations of the Al₂OH units and the last band to the Al₃OH units. In the 298 K Raman spectrum two intense bands are observed at 3547 and 3468 cm⁻¹” (Frost & Weier, 2004).

In Table 1 by Frost and Weier, we find the centers of the components of IR and Raman spectra of the hydroxyl stretching region as follows (in cm⁻¹):

IR	3646	3604	3550	3538	3469	3453	3326
Raman			3547		3468		

Raman fingerprint in Frost and Weier (cm⁻¹):

163 172 198 220 225 250 280 295 329 347 368 407 419 439 467 524 552 615 635 643
718 740 858 895 916 1006 1058 1089 1108 1136 1160 1355 1598 3468 3547

IR fingerprint in Frost and Weier (cm⁻¹):

546 605 631 645 714 786 830 893 928 1000 1009 1016 1070 1102 1142 1171 1204
1270 1315 1633 1787 2637 2845 3068 3326 3453 3469 3538 3550 3604 3646

RRUFF Data

Here we consider the Raman and IR data from the RRUFF Database.

<https://rruff.info/augelite/R050060>, <https://rruff.info/augelite/R050100> , and

<https://rruff.info/augelite/R050316> . The spectra are analyzed using q-Gaussian and q-BWF functions.

q-Gaussian function and its asymmetric q-BWF form

The fitting of Raman spectra with q-Gaussian line shapes has been proposed for the first time [in 2023](#) by A. C. Sparavigna. The q-Gaussian line shape is a function based on the Tsallis q-form of the exponential function (Tsallis, 1988). This exponential form is characterized by a q-parameter. When q is equal to 2, we have the Lorentzian function. If q is close to 1, we have a Gaussian function. For values of q between 1 and 2, we have a bell-shaped symmetric function with power-law wings ranging from Gaussian to Lorentzian tails.

The q-Gaussian is given as $f(x) = C e_q(-\gamma x^2)$, where $e_q(\cdot)$ is the q-exponential function and C a scale constant (Hanel et al., 2009). The q-exponential has expression: $e_q(u) = [1 + (1 - q)u]^{1/(1-q)}$. For spectroscopy, we write the q-Gaussian function with the center of the band at x_0 :

$$q\text{-Gaussian} = C \exp_q(-\gamma(x - x_0)^2) = C [1 + (q - 1)\gamma(x - x_0)^2]^{1/(1-q)}.$$

We can apply q-Gaussian functions by means of Fityk software. In Fityk, a q-Gaussian function can be defined in the following manner:

```
define Qgau(height, center, hwhm, q=1.5) = height*(1+(q-1)*((x-center)/hwhm)^2)^(1/(1-q))
```

where q=1.5 is the initial guessed value of the q-parameter. Parameter hwhm is the half width at half maximum of the line, in the case of a Lorentzian function. In fact, when q=2, the q-Gaussian turns into a Lorentzian function, that we can find defined in Fityk as:

```
Lorentzian(height, center, hwhm) = height/(1+((x-center)/hwhm)^2)
```

When q is close to 1, the q-Gaussian becomes a Gaussian function.

In Fityk, to define a function, use please Session > New Script > Blank Fityk Script

In the Blank Fityk Script paste the “define” of the function, for instance the Qgau given above.

Then, save the Script, and execute it. Using Functions > Definition Manager, in the list of the functions, it will be the q-Gaussian function too.

As shown on many occasions, the q-Gaussians are suitable for fitting Raman spectra (by examples proposed in [SSRN](#) to the [SERS](#) cases, for instance). For applying the q-Gaussians to [asymmetric bands](#), we can define also an asymmetric function, turning the Breit-Wigner-Fano (BWF) function into a q-BWF function (Sparavigna, 2023). Let us write the BWF as follow:

$$\text{BWF}(x) = C \frac{[1 - \xi \gamma^{1/2}(x - x_o)]^2}{[1 + \gamma(x - x_o)^2]}$$

When asymmetry parameter ξ is zero, BWF becomes a symmetric Lorentzian function. Note that the center of the line does not correspond to the position of the peak of the function. As in [Sparavigna, 2023](#), we can define the q-BWF function in the following manner:

$$\text{q-BWF} = C [1 - \xi \gamma^{1/2}(q - 1)^{1/2}(x - x_o)]^2 [1 + (q - 1)\gamma(x - x_o)^2]^{1/(1-q)}$$

In fact, the Lorentzian function is substituted by a q-Gaussian function. In Fityk, the [q-Breit-Wigner-Fano](#) (q-BWF) can be defined as:

$$\text{Qbreit}(\text{height}, \text{center}, \text{hwhm}, \text{q}=1.5, \text{xi}=0.1) = (1 - \text{xi} * (\text{q}-1) * (\text{x}-\text{center})/\text{hwhm})^2 * \text{height} * (1 + (\text{q}-1)^{0.5} * ((\text{x}-\text{center})/\text{hwhm})^2)^{1/(1-\text{q})}$$

And the BWF can be defined as:

$$\text{Breit}(\text{height}, \text{center}, \text{hwhm}, \text{xi}=0.1) = (1 - \text{xi} * (\text{x}-\text{center})/\text{hwhm})^2 * \text{height} / (1 + ((\text{x}-\text{center})/\text{hwhm})^2)$$

Using +xi instead of -xi does not change the fitting results in Fityk.

In the following work, we provide the Raman and ATR-IR spectral deconvolutions for Augelite in the form of screenshots of Fityk software, where the green dots are data from RRUFF, red curves the q-Gaussian components (or q-BWF components), yellow curve the sum of components. In the lower part of the screenshot, the misfit is given (difference between data and yellow curve). Supplementary material is providing folders containing .txt RRUFF data and the Fityk files .fit and .peaks, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15007132>

Raman fingerprint (Augelite R050060). Depolarized

https://rruff.info/repository/sample_child_record_raman/by_minerals/Augelite_R050060-3_Raman_514_0_depolarized_Raman_Data_Processed_25201.txt

Fig.1

#	PeakType	Center	Height (H>500)	H	Center	WHHM	q parameters...
%_24	Qgau	216.763	x	x	738.301	216.763	4.05476 0.999991
%_6	Qgau	225.583	x	x	3028.32	225.583	6.02219 1.04698
%_4	Qgau	251.414	x	x	3824.34	251.414	6.82602 1.45314
%_17	Qgau	351.234	x	x	613.165	351.234	10.1853 1.31975
%_9	Qgau	368.192	x	x	2418.2	368.192	6.67986 1.31329
%_7	Qgau	409.743	x	x	2801.68	409.743	8.44212 1.49828
%_35	Qgau	422.705	x	x	765.331	422.705	6.1434 1.38067
%_11	Qgau	464.297	x	x	1456.33	464.297	14.0251 1.00309
%_3	Qgau	526.748	x	x	4066.94	526.748	14.5725 1.00029
%_5	Qgau	563.562	x	x	3456.44	563.562	16.0634 1.32674
%_14	Qgau	624.654	x	x	1728.05	624.654	12.7263 1.52451
%_1	Qgau	636.3	x	x	12587.8	636.3	7.10766 1.58724
%_10	Qgau	858.827	x	x	2058.86	858.827	16.2615 1.72627
%_13	Qgau	895.782	x	x	928.148	895.782	9.48691 1.52133
%_15	Qgau	1014.05	x	x	860.874	1014.05	11.364 1.02579
%_12	Qgau	1063.42	x	x	1178.05	1063.42	17.9337 1.35978
%_27	Qgau	1089.51	x	x	897.684	1089.51	10.3581 1.00488
%_2	Qgau	1107.87	x	x	9226.76	1107.87	9.5329 1.39374
%_21	Qgau	1130.49	x	x	667.369	1130.49	13.7153 0.999939
%_8	Qgau	1161.86	x	x	2536.58	1161.86	12.6755 1.49055

Comparison with Raman fingerprint in Frost and Weier (cm^{-1}), **bold** within plus/minus 3 cm^{-1} :
 163 172 198 220 **225 250** 280 295 329 347 **368 407** 419 439 **467 524** 552 615 **635** 643
 718 740 **858 895** 916 1006 1058 1089 **1108** 1136 **1160** 1355 1598 3468 3547

Raman fingerprint (Augelite R050060). Broad Scan

Fig.2

#	PeakType	Center		Height (H>200=	Center	HWHM	q parameters...
%_36	Qgau	133.306	x	x	542.483	133.306	9.29973 1.00195
%_5	Qgau	163.373	x	x	3877.26	163.373	11.3818 1.69876
%_8	Qgau	224.241	x	x	2265.07	224.241	9.77789 1.47647
%_25	Qgau	249.305	x	x	206.428	249.305	9.32577 2.20303
%_11	Qgau	330.628	x	x	948.267	330.628	14.4331 1.5669
%_15	Qgau	368.346	x	x	713.346	368.346	10.8594 1.42268
%_7	Qgau	415.912	x	x	2402.06	415.912	16.9106 1.00075
%_10	Qgau	461.488	x	x	1172.78	461.488	28.7571 1.00095
%_6	Qgau	526.195	x	x	2741.11	526.195	15.9406 1.484
%_16	Qgau	553.889	x	x	598.498	553.889	25.7254 2.24611
%_2	Qgau	636.751	x	x	7809.94	636.751	9.56 1.75731
%_20	Qgau	741.483	x	x	349.199	741.483	11.1168 1.05179
%_29	Qgau	860.762	x	x	340.831	860.762	17.8591 1.56969
%_17	Qgau	897.199	x	x	435.091	897.199	10.6926 1.90193
%_22	Qgau	1012.53	x	x	243.166	1012.53	14.0778 2.93074
%_14	Qgau	1059.94	x	x	875.64	1059.94	11.8409 3.21749
%_4	Qgau	1111.09	x	x	6453.37	1111.09	11.9464 1.72525
%_12	Qgau	1149.03	x	x	1004.01	1149.03	29.7097 1.00513
%_44	Qgau	3429.89	x	x	560.362	3429.89	57.9243 1.37872
%_3	Qgau	3468.74	x	x	7753.3	3468.74	11.0716 2.59051
%_46	Qgau	3507.71	x	x	2679.29	3507.71	27.0491 1.00054
%_47	Qgau	3527.75	x	x	668.241	3527.75	10.3623 1.71589
%_1	Qgau	3549.66	x	x	10970.8	3549.66	19.3946 1.72895
%_38	Qgau	3637.4	x	x	288.209	3637.4	62.1385 1.21635
%_40	Qgau	4097.67	x	x	236.532	4097.67	175.554 1.00132
%_41	Qgau	4384.12	x	x	371.284	4384.12	234.717 1.66325

Comparison with Raman fingerprint in Frost and Weier (cm⁻¹), bold within plus/minus 5 cm⁻¹:
163 172 198 **220** **225** 250 280 295 **329** 347 **368** 407 **419** 439 467 **524** **552** 615 **635** 643
 718 **740** **858** **895** 916 1006 **1058** 1089 **1108** 1136 1160 1355 1598 **3468** **3547**

The following two images show the hydroxyl stretching region. The first is obtained with five q-Gaussian function, the second with three q-Gaussians.

Fig.3

Fig.4

Increasing the number of components improves the misfit.

IR fingerprint (Augelite R050060)

Fig.5

Fig.6

The two previous screenshots are showing the deconvolution of the ATR-IR spectrum obtained by q-BWF functions, that is the asymmetric version of the q-Gaussian functions. Note the white dots: they represent the 'center' of the function, which is not coincident with the peak of the function.

The peaks are at (cm^{-1}):

383.5 431 544.5 606 635.5 714 830 921 1008 1072 1103 1142 1198 3467 3478 3546 3606

Let us compare with IR fingerprint in Frost and Weier (cm^{-1}) (bold within plus/minus 5 cm^{-1})

546 605 631 645 **714** 786 **830** 893 928 1000 **1009** 1016 **1070 1102 1142** 1171 **1204**

1270 1315 1633 1787 2637 2845 3068 3326 3453 3469 3538 **3550 3604** 3646

Let us stress that here we have used asymmetric functions (q-BWF functions), whereas Frost and Weier used symmetric functions for the deconvolution.

IR fingerprint (Augelite R050100)

Fig.7

The peaks R050100 are at (cm^{-1}):

403 429 545 616 634 714 829 921 1010 1072 1102 1143 1197 2960 3467 3488 3544 3606

Let us report the peaks of R050060:

383.5 431 544.5 606 635.5 714 830 921 1008 1072 1103 1142 1198 3467 3478 3546 3606

IR fingerprint (Augelite R050316)

Fig.8

The peaks R050316 are at (cm⁻¹):

385 397 432 450 490 542 607 632 713 830 894 922 952 1004 1035 1063 1095 1127 1151 1192
3464 3483 3547 3585 3614

Let us report the peaks of R050100:

403 429 545 616 634 714 829 921 1010 1072 1102 1143 1197
2960 3467 3488 3544 3606

And of R050060:

383.5 431 544.5 606 635.5 714 830 921 1008 1072 1103 1142 1198
3467 3478 3546 3606

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